

Dingaling Indian Dance Festivals and Triggering International Tourist Inflow

Dr. Prabhu Kumari Vanama

Associate Professor, Department of Historical Studies
Government Arts College for Men (A), CHENNAI – 600 035

ABSTRACT

India, the land of cultural confluence makes it as a chosen destination to visit and tour by the tourists of class kind as well as the mass mind. Tourists from any corner of India, be it south or north, east or west and from any part of the world whether Asia or America, Africa or Antarctica and Europe or Australia throng to India to drench their cultural appetite. As India is the land suitable to visit throughout the year, tourists often opt to visit the various destinations of India during the seasons when cultural performances take place. As there is no dearth for dance festivals be it a typical classical show or a common unconventional environment, tourists throng to India to witness these festivals and many a times they also actively participate in these cultural events. Besides, the country also has no dearth of dances of local genre as they give an opportunity to the folks of Indian origin and foreign to participate lively during their visits to those places. A peep into the international tourist inflow into India, if minutely probed explicitly reveals that they flock to India in the months when dance festivals are performed.

Key Words: Cultural confluence, Cultural events, Cultural appetite, cultural performances,
Cultural appetite, Dance festivals

Introduction

Having classical dances as the base of different genre, the Government of India with its' tourism departments is organizing typical conventional dance festivals at various States such as Hampi Dance Utsav, Khajuraho Festival, Konark Dance Festival, Mamallapuram Utsav, Nishagandhi Dance Festival, Natyanjali Utsav, Taj Mahotsav and so on. This study depicts how and when these festivals being organized in various States of India, say it North or South, East or West, serves as the required pull and push to clinch the tourists who willingly cling to India to witness them.

The Limitations:

As India is the vast land of multifarious languages, traditions and customs, quite a number of dance festivals are being conducted regionally and locally throughout the length and breadth of the country. Hence, this study is restricted to only national classical dance festivals conducted by the Department of Tourism, Government of India.

Hampi Utsava:

Hampi Utsava is conducted at the UNESCO world heritage site situated in the land mass of central Karnataka. The Karnataka State Government recreates the cultural grandeur of the erstwhile Vijayanagar empire in the month of January¹, here with the dance performances of the prominent and professional artists of India. The ruins of Hampi, echoes with the live sounds of music and dance which is understood as being performed right from the days of Vijayanagar. No wonder, it is believed to be started and continued till date from the erstwhile days of the Vijayanagar empire to celebrate their victory in the guise of *Vijaya Utsava*² and is considered as the oldest celebrations of India being conducted to demonstrate the cultural and royal grandeur of the Vijayanagar emperors continuously for a week.³

REFERENCES:

1. <https://traveltriangle.com/blog/hampi-utsav/>
2. ²“Khajuraho mein Shaasthreey Nrithy kaa Melaa” in *BBC News*, 6 February 2018
3. ³<https://www.karnataka.com/hampi/hampi-festival/>

During the days when these dance shows are conducted, impeccable lighting arrangements will be created throughout the length and breadth of the Tungabhadra banks where the illuminated Hampi monuments and ruins can be visualised. Being furthered with various heart throbbing attractive competitions organized for Mehendi and photography, sporting activity in the waters of the Tungabhadra river, puppetry shows, food courts, fireworks and exhibitions, this tourist destination attracts lakhs of visitors every year. The spectacular attraction of this event is Jambu Safari or the grand procession of the elephants and men adorned in the attire of the Vijayanagar kingdom soldiers.

A Cultural Ode to the Vijayanagar Legacy

Other distinctive attractions include giving an opportunity to the versatile folk performers making the Hampi Utsava enjoyable to the connoisseur and the commoner. Ofcourse spectacular fireworks, cultural shows ranging from drama and puppet shows to music performances coupled with the *Jambu Safari* i.e., a procession of elephants and people adorned in the attire of Vijayanagar soldiers. To meet the rapid technological pace of the modern day, helicopter rides are arranged for aerial visit and to reach the prospects of the common herd fireworks, exhibitions, puppet shows, shopping too.

The Khajuraho Dance Festival:

The Khajuraho Dance Festival celebrated in the month of February from 20th to 26th every year is organised by the Madhya Pradesh Kala Parishad. It is a festival of classical dances

celebrated consecutively for a week annually alongside the Khajuraho group of temples⁴ in the State of Madhya Pradesh.⁵ This festival highlights the richness of the Indian classical as well as folk dance styles with performances of some of the best exponents in the field. An interesting but heart throbbing feature of this festival is that it balances the pendulum of classical and folk dances on one side and the modern dances on the other equivocally. Here, the dances are performed in an open-air auditorium situated in front of the Sun God temple who is otherwise styled as Chitragupta and the Vishvanatha Temple dedicated to Lord Shiva.

Spectacular intriguing and a week long trips are arranged under the guise of *Namaste India Trip*⁶, which throws open the magical ambience of cultural extravaganza comprising of Bharathanatyam, Kathak, Kuchipudi, Mohiniyattam, Odissi in an open-air theatre.

A Dancer dancing in the ambience of Khajuraho temple

Konark Dance Festival:

At the World Heritage Site acclaimed as one of the seven wonders of India, the Konark Dance festival is conducted in the precincts of popularly acclaimed Sun Temple. Unabatedly being conducted significantly from the year of 1986, the Konark Dance Festival (KDF) takes place for 5 days from 1st to 5th of December takes

4. ⁴Gilles Beguin, Lago Carazza, Christophe Hioco and Luca Poggi, *Khajuraho – Indian Temples and Sensuous Sculptures* (Milan, 2017), p.
5. ⁵"So much divine energy in Khajuraho Danseuse Methil Devika" in *Toronto Telegraph*, 3 April 2018
6. ⁶<https://www.namasteholiday.com/khajuraho.html>

place in an open air auditorium⁷. This dance festival showcases the traditional cultural depth of India in the global level. Exponents and enthusiasts of all dance genre say it from the main land and even remote and border areas such as Assam throng to this dance carnival and add appeal as well as luster to this classical event. Bedecked with crafts mela, this event publicises the Odisha's cultural heritage.⁸⁹

Nishagandhi Dance Festival:

Nishagandhi Dance Festival having been organized by the Kerala Tourism Development Corporation, is celebrated in the environs of the South Indian State Kerala, quite uniquely in none of the temples as usually dance festivals are organized, but, in a spectacular architectural extravaganza of historic Kanakakunnu palace, located at Thiruvananthapuram or Trivandrum in the month of January.

Kalaeidoscopic classical dancers of Kerala performing Mohiniattam

The multi-hued Indian performing artists multifariously and meticulously enthrall and appeal the observers with their mesmerizing dance performances. Besides, this venue has a unique heritage of having been situated in the capital city of Trivandrum in Kanakakunnu Palace.

7. ⁷<https://www.outlookindia.com/traveller/tag/konark-dance-festival/>

8. ⁸<https://odishatourism.gov.in/>

9. ⁹Konarkfestival.com

It is heart throbbing that Nishagandhi Dance festival opens its' platform to the stalwarts as well as to the budding artists who are immersed with artistic zeal. No wonder, entry fee to this startling magnetic dance festival too is free¹⁰.

Taj Mahotsav:

The world renowned Taj Mahotsav celebrated for 10 consecutive days usually in the month of February as one of the new seven wonders of the world is an architectural magnum opus of its' day. This cultural bonanza not only provides a visual feast of dance to the viewers, but also becomes the homeland for nearly 400 artisans who flock to Taj to display their exquisite works of art and craft. Performing arts intertwined with the architectural extravaganza of the country turns this Mahotsav as a typically sought event by the foreigners of any origin¹¹.

Mamallapuram Dance Festival:

Resting amidst the Bay of Bengal and the Great Salt Lake in the tranquilising State of Tamil Nadu, the port town Mahabalipuram situated 57km. from the historic city of Chennai, hosts the mesmerizing *Mamallapuram Dance Festival* mostly in the month of January, under the auspices of The Tamil Nadu Tourism Development Corporation. The venue is the way forward for both the classical as well as folk dance heritage of India. Being visualized at the backdrop of *Arjuna's Penance*, the performances performed here instill a poignant divine and mystical feeling in the eyes and the minds of the observers.

The breathtaking dances are performed in ornamented stage with the historic stone sculptures range "the Arjuna Penance" as the backdrop. The whole scene is mystical seems

10. ¹⁰<https://www.indianholiday.com/fairs-and-festivals/kerala/nisha-gandhi-dance-festival.html>

11. ¹¹<http://www.tajmahotsav.org/>

*to be happening amidst a dreamy ambiance.*¹²

The Pallava carvings of the 7th and the 8th century significantly draws a huge crowd throughout the year from the length and breadth of the country and from all over the globe. A ubiquitous feature of this dance festival is that it surprises its viewers with a plethora of temples, monuments. These peerless Pallava architectural pieces dating back to 7th century are annually embedded with sensitizing and surprising classical as well as folk dances of the genre, squirrels the artistic senses of the class as well as the mass irrespective of the region they belong to. The plethora of temples and monuments in a never ending golden sand shores of ceaseless roaring waves of Mahabalipuram embedded with rich culture rejuvenates the touring moments of the viewers and encourages as well as satiates the thirst of folk dance forms of India too. During this fest, viewers of distinct aegis quench their thirst for art on a single platform as both the classical and folk dancers gets equal opportunity to showcase their art here.

*Those who love art forms, those who are passionate folk lovers, and those who like to enjoy the rich heritage of India, Mamallapuram festival is where you need to be to satiate your hunger. This arena provides an excellent experience and keen peek through the culture of South India.*¹³

One of its kind extravaganza of folk dance forms, the Mamallapuram Dance Festival will surely worth your expectations and even better than you have imagined. This platform is a perfect one-stop destination to witness the cultural and heritage beauty of the state of Tamil Nadu in general and that of Mahabalipuram in particular. This festival brings out the glory of different dance forms and inculcates the seed of passion in every onlooker. Wait no more get mesmerized by the peerless dances of veteran artists at a romantic destination.

Thus, Mahabalipuram dance festival casts a great fest to the onlookers and also takes great measures in keeping alive the various folk forms of India. It is the most splendid festival

12. ¹²<https://www.tamilnadutourism.com/blog/mamallapuram-dance-festival/#:~:text=This%20festival%20is%20nothing%20but,Arjuna%20Penance%E2%80%9D%20as%20the%20backdrop>, 19, December 2019

15. Ibid.

for both the dancers and dance passionate. It can also be a great weekend destination to take your kids and make them known about our rich culture. And also the best place to spend some memorable time with friends and family.

Natyanjali Dance Festival:

Usually celebrated in the month of February at Chidambaram in the State of Tamil Nadu, the Natyanjali Dance Festival is considered as the most celestial space to perform as danseuse or danseuses gets an opportunity to dance in the ancient sacred spot of the frontage of the God of dance i.e., Lord Nataraja or the dancing Lord Shive. This holy shrine of Lord Nataraja is of immense esoteric and spiritual significance as this is the only place where Lord Shiva can be worshipped in the form of dancing God or Lord Nataraja. Lord Nataraja here is in the posture of Ananda (happy) Tandava Nataraja¹⁴ depicting the five-fold acts of Almighty i.e., Creation, Protection, Transformation, Containment or Screening and grace.

The exquisite beauty and aesthetic nuance of Lord Nataraja here is the perennial source of inspiration for the dancers of any time and clime from the time immemorial. To venerate the ecstasy and the divinity of dancing Lord Nataraja through the medium of dance to which the Lord here is the God, every year the distinct dancers from nooks and corners of the world throng and express their devotion in the form of *Natyanjali* i.e., *Natya* (dance) and *Anjali* (Worship). As such this Natyanjali has grown in popularity by leaps and bounds. From the year 1981, this event has been transformed into a 5 days national fest, which is jointly organized by the Natyanjali Trust¹⁵ and the Government. Here around 300 to 400 dancers with accompanying

16. Uday Dokras, “Chidambaram – Sri Thillai Nataraja Temple” in *Journal of the Indo Nordic Author’s Collective* (2020), pp. 25ff

17. <http://www.natyanjalichidambaram.com/>

18. Karishma Sen, “India Developing Cultural Tourism through Festivals”, in *T3 Travel Trends Today*, 8 March 2016

artists gets an opportunity to perform along with other accompanying artistes. An entry into this dance fest acquired international dimension from the yester years.

Dance Fests Boosting Tourist Inflow:

Any industry can be considered as a successful industry only based on its' popular demand. Tourism industry too is a no exception to this. Here arises the continuous need for novelty that can be classically but peculiarly meted out by clubbing performing arts especially dance with tourism. To quote Subhash Goyal, President of the Indian Association of Tour Operators,

Festivals have the potential to extend tourist seasons, peak seasons and introduce a “new season” for a destination¹⁶.

So, the appealing beauty of the architecture, landmass clubbed with the aesthetics of the performing arts especially dance, can continuously remain as the clinging knot to clinch the tourists towards mother India. The below given table surmises the inflow of foreign tourists into India reaching more during the second half of the year when the popular international dance fests took place irrespective of the endemic pandemic, compared to the months when there are no live performances in India.

Peak Months of Foreign Tourist Arrivals Into India From Top 15 Countries in 2021 During The Season of Dance Fests

S. No	Nationality	Lean Month (% Share)	Peak Month (% Share)
1	United States	May (1.61%)	Dec (23.28%)
2	Bangladesh	May (0.04%)	Dec (19.24%)
3	United Kingdom	May (0.81%)	Dec (22.20%)
4	Canada	May (0.61%)	Dec (24.16%)
5	Nepal	May (1.17%)	Oct (13.61%)

6	Afghanistan	Sep & Nov (0.5%)	Mar (21.41%)
7	Australia	May (0.31%)	Dec (51.74%)
8	Germany	May (1.49%)	Dec (15.90%)
9	Portugal	May (2.50%)	Nov (16.22%)
10	France	May (2.69%)	Nov (14.21%)
11	Maldives	May (0.89) %)	Dec (28.47%)
12	Sri Lanka	May (0.44%)	Dec (38.91%)
13	Russia Fed	May (2.21%)	Dec (25.31%)
14	Iraq	May (0.06%)	Jan (13.95%)
15	Netherlands	May (3.57%)	Dec (18.41%)

Source: Bureau of Immigration, India

The above given table depicts that the number of Foreign Tourist Arrivals to India in 2021 during the months when the Dance Festivals takes place was the highest as they get an opportunity to witness the lively and stirring aesthetics along with the immortal and immovable architecture rose more than 50% even during the endemic pandemic period. As such, dance is the hidden language of the soul that quenches the inner aesthetic intent and clubbing of this aesthetic art with intangible tourism tangibly augments the Indian economy and esteem to impeccable heights. Hence this study.